

AIRCRAFT NOISE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN EASTERN EUROPEAN COUNTRIES

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ABSTRACT:

Aircraft Noise Management is a rather new concern in countries from the Eastern region of Europe, in comparison with other European regions. This statement is supported by the few interventions that have been implemented up to the present moment, situation that facilitates various opportunities for most of the relevant stakeholders (e.g. land-use planning).

In order to be able to understand the importance of Aircraft Noise Management in this region, the article starts with a description of previous and predicted air traffic growth in comparison with other European countries. Further, the core legislative support for Aircraft Noise Management in Romania, Slovenia and Ukraine is detailed, followed by representative 'best practice' experiences at the level of each country.

The article ends with highlighting the conclusions from experiences of the three countries as a basis for 'lesson learning'.

1. INTRODUCTION

From 2009 to 2017, air traffic growth in Europe faced an overall stagnation period. In spite of this situation, the countries located in the Eastern side of Europe managed to accomplish growth rates of 3% or higher, during the same period of time when the rest of the European countries reached an average of 1% or below [1]. Through the analysis of air traffic demand and various influencing factors, the traffic growth forecast up to 2040 is predominantly expected to be higher in the Eastern European countries.

Figure 1. Growth forecast to 2040 (IFR movements) in Regulation and Growth shows differences between Western and Eastern rates (the same is true in other scenarios).[1]

Air traffic growth is directly influenced by the available capacity of airports. This relationship is highly relevant for research regarding airport and aircraft environmental challenges, since an airport reaching its capacity limits determines a significant increase in airport congestions, consequently an increase in the number of delays and a potential stagnation of air traffic growth. In such cases, when the number of delays is increased, measures designed to deal with environmental issues that are directly dependant on the number of aircraft operations or on the interval of operation (day, evening, night) may result in outcomes different from the initial expectations.

Throughout the years, aircraft noise has become the "most significant cause of adverse community reaction related to the operation and expansion of airports" [2]. The importance of understanding the level of knowledge and practice on tackling aircraft noise challenges in this region is key to identifying the needs of airports and stakeholders in defining common opportunities for managing noise by having a preventative, rather than a mitigation

approach.

In-depth research on Aircraft Noise Management, including practices from this European region, has been recently performed under the framework of ANIMA (Aviation Noise Impact Management through Novel Approaches) EU Horizon 2020 funded research project [3]. Experiences of airports from various European countries have been documented in order to understand the different levels of Noise Management implementation and to explore the variety of interventions and approaches considered in reducing and/or preventing the exposure and impact of aircraft noise. Key findings have shown that most countries from Eastern Europe are in the early stages of developing noise interventions, when compared to other countries from different European regions (e.g. Germany, United Kingdom).

For the purpose of this article, three countries were selected for discussion, i.e. Romania, Slovenia and Ukraine.

2. NOISE RELATED LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORKS IN EASTERN EUROPE

The Environmental Noise Directive, i.e. Directive 2002/49/EC [4], is the common legislative framework related to aircraft noise in all Member States of the European Union. It originates from the 1996 Green Paper on Future Noise Policy [5] and aims to “define a common approach intended to avoid, prevent or reduce on a prioritised basis, the harmful effects, including annoyance, due to environmental noise” [4] from major noise sources, including aircraft.

The main requirements of the Environmental Noise Directive include noise mapping, together with the development of Strategic Noise Maps and Noise Action Plans, on a 5-year basis, for airports having more than 50,000 movements/year to assess, reduce and prevent the exposure of the population to noise. This approach ensures the provision of a common basis for action against noise exposure for all Member States of the European Union. However, the implementation of the Directive is different from one Member State to another, due to their distinct legislations, policies and practices at the National level.

The Environmental Noise Directive was transposed in 2004 in Slovenia [6] and in 2005 in Romania [7], while in Ukraine not at all.

Limit values in Slovenia and Romania are focused on the determination of four noise indicators (L_{den} , L_{day} , $L_{evening}$ and L_{night}), under the transposition of the Environmental Noise Directive. In the first case, the limits are split in two categories of airports, having more or less than 50,000 movements/year, yet all Slovenian airports have under that requirement, therefore none can be classified as being a ‘major airport’.

Table 1. Limit values in Slovenia [8]

Limit values for airports having less than 50,000 movements/year		
L_{den}/L_{day} [dBA]	$L_{evening}$ [dBA]	L_{night} [dBA]
58	53	48
Limit values for airports having more than 50,000 movements/year		
L_{den}/L_{day} [dBA]	$L_{evening}$ [dBA]	L_{night} [dBA]
65	60	55

In the case of Romania, the maximum allowed values for L_{den} and L_{night} are of 70 dBA, respectively 60 dBA [9]. In 2005, when the Environmental Noise Directive was transposed within the Romanian legislative framework [7], one airport (i.e. “Henri Coanda” International Airport) qualified as being a ‘major airport’, thus it was the sole airport falling under the requirements of this Directive. Ever since, 10 additional airports, designated as ‘urban airports’, were included under the compliance of the Directive, after several amendments to the National transposition of the Directive. These airports are the following: Bucharest (Baneasa) – Aurel Vlaicu International Airport, Avram Iancu (Cluj) International Airport, Iasi International Airport, Craiova International Airport, Oradea International Airport, Sibiu International Airport, Transilvania (Targu Mures) International Airport, Maramures (Baia Mare) International Airport, George Enescu (Bacau) International Airport and Satu Mare International Airport. The ‘urban airport’ designation was attributed to airports located within or in the proximity of agglomerations that qualify as urban areas, with the main purpose of approaching preventative measures on airports with less than 50,000 movements/year and with significant expected air traffic growth and infrastructure expansions. As a consequence, 11 Romanian airports have undertaken noise mapping and have developed and submitted Strategic Noise Maps and Noise Action Plans for the last reporting period required by the Directive.

In Ukraine, Strategic Noise Maps and Noise Action Plans are absent. However, all certified airports/aerodromes have to develop noise maps under the requirements of Noise Protection Zones, regulated at a National level [10]. If an analysis was to be performed with respect to the criteria and requirements of the Environmental Noise Directive, Ukraine has only one airport that can qualify as being a ‘major airport’ (Boryspil International Airport).

Noise levels are regulated with respect to restrictions for constructions around civil airports for the day time (0700-2300) and night time (2300-0700), designating the areas as “Unsuitable for Construction”, “Protection against noise” and “Limitations for residential construction” [11].

Out of the three countries selected for this study, two (Romania and Slovenia) have transposed the provisions of the Environmental Noise Directive

within their National legislative framework. One important aspect to take into consideration is the fact that the compliance of Ukraine with the Directive is voluntary. However, it has approached aircraft noise through various measures similar to the provisions of the Directive, such as the development of noise maps and the introduction of noise limits. Differences between the approach of the three countries on Aircraft Noise Management can be observed from the formulation of noise limits. In Ukraine, the aim of noise limits is to focus on imposing restrictions for constructions in the vicinity of airports through the use of prediction noise maps. In Romania and Slovenia, the noise limits act as reinforcers for interventions to reduce noise exposure through the use of noise maps from past operations.

3. NOISE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES FROM THE EASTERN REGION OF EUROPE

3.1. Aircraft Noise Management Review - Romania

A high air traffic growth is expected in Romania, with an estimated average between 2% and 5.6% [12] until 2024.

Figure 2. Evolution of traffic in Romania [12]

According to the last amendments of the National Governmental Decision transposing the Environmental Noise Directive, aside from airports having more than 50,000 movements/year, 10 additional urban airports must be compliant with the provisions of the Directive, as they are located in the vicinity or within agglomerations classified as urban areas. Therefore, a total of 11 Romanian airports had to develop Strategic Noise Maps and Noise Action Plans for the last reporting period required by the Directive.

Apart from the transposition of the Directive, the applicable National legislative framework lacks any other provision related to the management of aircraft noise.

Under the measures proposed within Noise Action Plans, for maintaining and/or reducing the number of people exposed to aircraft noise, most airports have highlighted the intention to collaborate with the National, regional and Local Authorities in

order to contribute to the development of a comprehensive legislative framework in this area. Many statements focused on the need to correlate land-use planning with noise contours from noise maps, as a measure to maintain and/or reduce the number of people exposed to noise [13][14]. In reaction to these statements, the Ministry of Environment took the initiative to clarify several provisions from the Governmental Decision transposing the Environmental Noise Directive and to enforce the collaboration between the relevant stakeholders for the management of noise through launching a Noise Law Project. While drafting the provisions of the new Noise Law [15], published in 2019, several consultations were held with all relevant parties. Its special character resides in the transposition of some provisions from the INSPIRE Directive [16], considered useful for noise management. In addition, it describes a direct connection with the Regulation (EU) No. 598/2014 [17], therefore it enforces the implementation of ICAO Balanced Approach [7] principles.

Some relevant improvements from the first transposition of the Directive include a stronger emphasis on the importance of collaborative action for noise management. Specifically, in the case of aircraft noise, various other stakeholders are now officially required to contribute to noise management. Apart from the Economic Operator of the airport, the Air Navigation Service Provider and the Civil Aviation Authority are included as being the main stakeholders for aircraft noise management from the aviation sector. Before the 2019 Noise Law, the Economic Operator of the airport was the sole responsible for managing aircraft noise.

Land-use planning provisions related to noise are still incomplete, yet some aspects are expected to be included in the amendment of the Air Code, which should be published in 2020.

3.2. Aircraft Noise Management Review - Slovenia

Slovenia, from the position of a Member State of the European Union, has transposed the Environmental Noise Directive within their National legislative framework since 2004 [6]. As a consequence, all Slovenian airports having more than 50,000 movements/year have to be compliant with the provisions of the Directive. However, no Slovenian airport fulfils this criterion and only one airport is expected to exceed this value in 2020 [18].

In the case of Slovenia, the focus of the article is on the largest Slovenian International airport, which is Ljubljana Jože Pučnik Airport. The airport is under the ownership of Fraport Slovenija, which is also in the possession of several parts of the land in the vicinity of the airport, thus enabling the opportunities for airport expansions and auxiliary constructions.

The first attempts on addressing environmental issues were focused on the implementation of an Environmental Management System and on the development of Sustainability Reports [18]. In this respect, a systematic collection of all contributions supporting a sustainable development was designed and implemented for the first time, in line with the requirements of the Environmental Management System.

Since 2015, Sustainability Reports have been developed on an annual basis, as a main communication resource to reach out to local communities located near the airport and to the overall public. From their early development, Sustainability Reports aimed to ensure an effective and transparent communication inside and outside the organisation, in order to build a culture of sustainability.

The content of the reports has been developed as an opportunity to communicate in a transparent manner the focus of the management of the airport on the direct impact of the operations on economic, social and environmental matters, while acknowledging the negative environmental impact of operations and committing to address the resulting environmental issues.

All reports describe the daily operations of the company, together with their involvement in dealing with environmental issues, in order to emphasise the benefits and opportunities from past, current and future operations and their efforts to deal with environmental matters, including aircraft noise.

The decisions regarding the information that should be included within the reports are based on data analysis through the use of a "Matrix of Materiality" [18], developed internally. The criteria used for the selection of information include the sustainable context, the level of engagement of stakeholders and the relevance of the topic. Furthermore, further analyses are performed by various departments of the organisation and an environmental expert, based on additional sub criteria such as balance, reliability of data, clarity, accuracy and comparability. The use of this tool supports an in-depth understanding and management of the organisation in a sustainable manner, by addressing all relevant aspects and concerns, from environmental to economic and social.

From the outcomes of the "Matrix of Materiality", the stakeholder groups relevant for the operations of the organisation were defined: State and EU bodies, owners, business partners, employees, passengers and visitors, local communities and Media.

Results from recorded complaints and from several noise monitoring activities determined that noise has become the main environmental issue for both the airport and the neighbouring communities. In this regard, key materiality areas for

communication have been formulated based on continuous dialogue with representatives of the stakeholder groups and through the use of GRI Guidelines [19] to address the concerns and account for the needs of all relevant parties. Therefore, the goals established by the airport aim to represent all relevant stakeholders throughout daily operations. As an example, the formulated objectives of the airport vary from ensuring the satisfaction and motivation of employees to establishing and maintaining good relations with all stakeholders to support obtaining a high-quality environment for neighbouring communities.

Through the use of these reports, the efforts to deal with aircraft noise have been described, starting with awareness content included to facilitate effective communication with local communities (e.g. phone, e-mail, Social Media, online forms, regular meetings). Such communication means are managed as an integrated part of the Quality Management System of the organisation. One relevant outcome of the effectiveness of communication was the installation of a natural noise-reduction barrier through a partnership between the airport and the Šenčur local community.

3.3. Aircraft Noise Management Review - Ukraine

In Ukraine, airports are responsible for the development of maps in compliance with four Protection Zones, the Noise Protection Zone for noise, the Public Safety Zone for third party risk, the Sanitary Protection Zone for local air pollution and the EM Protection zone for electro-magnetic fields. The development of the maps is a mandatory requirement for airport/aerodrome certification, therefore the airport/ aerodrome operations have to be correlated with the use of the land and the health of the population living in its vicinity.

General practices related to Aircraft Noise Management are mainly related to the development of noise maps considering past and scheduled operations, which are further included within an explanatory report that details the impact of aircraft noise in both scenarios.

Noise maps are developed through the use of computer modelling techniques, without noise measurements. The development process accounts for various factors, such as the number of aircraft movements, the fleet mix, the expected fleet changes, the expected number of scrapped aircraft, the possibility of opening new routes, potential infrastructure changes and others. Through the use of the aforementioned factors, prediction noise maps are developed for the next 5, 10 and 15 years, together with a scenario for the maximum operational capacity of the airport. Noise maps are further included in reports that can contribute to the development of strategies for

land-use planning in the proximity of the airport, as such information can provide essential insight into opportunities for air traffic growth, airport expansions and protection of human health.

The development of different scenarios of noise exposure depending on the past, current and future aircraft operations contributes to establishing the boundaries of aircraft noise under the Noise Protection Zone. These boundaries are further translated into restrictions for the development of buildings. L_{eq} and L_{Amax} are the noise indicators in use for obtaining average and maximum noise exposure scenarios.

Table 2. Restrictions for constructions around civil airports according to Ukrainian legislations [11]

Restriction Types		Unsuitable for construction	Protection against noise	Limitations for residential construction
Day time	L_{AeqD} [dBA]	≥ 75	< 75 ≥ 65	< 65 ≥ 55
	$L_{Amax D}$ [dBA]	≥ 90	< 90 ≥ 80	< 80 ≥ 70
Night time	L_{AeqN} [dBA]	≥ 65	< 65 ≥ 55	< 55 ≥ 45
	$L_{Amax N}$ [dBA]	≥ 80	< 80 ≥ 70	< 70 ≥ 60

4. CONCLUSIONS AND LESSONS LEARNT

Workshops and periodic meetings between relevant stakeholders related to the awareness and understanding of aircraft noise exposure and impact can support the common understanding of notions and, consequently can improve the decision-making, implementation and evaluation of interventions.

Aircraft Noise Management can be either approached as an integrated process, as in the case of Ukraine, which is included from the core functioning processes of airport operations, or as a component of the Environmental Management System, as it is the case in Romania and Slovenia. Prediction noise maps and scenarios of noise exposure based on current aircraft operations and on an air traffic forecast, can be a useful tool in supporting strategic decision-making that accounts for both population health and potential airport expansions.

Communication and collaboration between all stakeholders relevant for aircraft noise can support the development and improvement of effective National legislative frameworks. In addition, effective communication can support the airport and local communities to benefit from favourable economic conditions and existing opportunities in a sustainable manner.

Dissemination of efforts in dealing with aircraft noise, in relation with noise monitoring results, can contribute to establishing a relationship between the airport and local communities based on trust and transparency.

Noise Complaint Management, together with a

systematic data collection system and the development of official and/or dedicated reports for raising awareness and promoting implemented and proposed interventions can help in understanding the current noise situation and can contribute to further decision-making processes, as well as to the implementation of any further interventions.

Guidance related to criteria related to effective implementation of interventions to reduce and/or prevent the noise impact and noise exposure is insufficient, therefore further in-depth research on the experience of other airports dealing with aircraft noise is needed, especially on the complexity of factors involved in this process.

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